

THE ROLE AND MECHANISMS OF CRITICAL THINKING IN POLITICAL DECISION-MAKING

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Abstract: This thesis analyzes the role and importance of critical thinking in political decision-making. Since political decisions have a direct impact on the social stability and trust of society, the culture of critical thinking should be given special attention in the decision-making process. The thesis examines the essence of critical thinking, its place in political thinking, as well as the competencies necessary for politicians and civil servants. Methods that contribute to the development of critical thinking, such as analytical trainings, scenario analysis, Delphi methodology, and information critical filters, are also presented. This work also presents proposals for developing a culture of critical thinking, analyzing political decisions, and increasing moral responsibility.

Keywords: Political decision, critical thinking, logical analysis, moral responsibility, political thinking, analytical thinking, scenario analysis, information manipulation, democracy, political institutions, Uzbekistan.

Political decision-making is one of the most responsible forms of human thinking. Such decisions directly affect not only the political system, but also the social stability and trust of society as a whole. Therefore, the presence of a culture of critical thinking in the decision-making process is of decisive importance.

Critical thinking is the ability to deeply analyze facts, evaluate grounds and evidence, distinguish subjective opinions, and foresee consequences. John Dewey described this process as “a conscious, consistent, and goal-oriented form of thinking” [2]. In his opinion, if a person does not think critically, then any democratic institution will become mechanical. When making a political decision, it is necessary to approach it based on evidence and analysis, not on emotional or party interests. Aristotle already said that “unreasonable politics falls under the dominance of passions”. Therefore, critical thinking is a central element of political thought. The prominent sociologist of the 20th century, M. Weber, put forward the concept of “ethics of responsibility”, emphasizing that a politician must combine two main criteria in decision-making - logical justification and moral responsibility [3]. This approach includes not only the intellectual, but also the moral component of critical thinking.

Critically thinking politician:

1. Evaluates and analyzes data;
2. Predicts the consequences of each decision;
3. Compares alternative solutions and selects the most optimal one;
4. Recognizes errors and creates a correction mechanism.

Such an approach increases the transparency of political decisions and citizens' trust.

In today's era of globalization, the political environment is full of multi-layered information flows, disinformation, and populist rhetoric. In these circumstances, critical thinking is the strongest intellectual defense for a politician.

American philosopher Karl Popper interpreted democracy as a “system capable of accepting criticism” [4]. In the Popperan approach, the strength of the political system depends on its openness in decision-making and the ability for self-correction. Therefore, critical thinking is an internal control mechanism of the political system.

The lack of critical thinking in the process of political decision-making leads to the following consequences:

- Decision-making based on emotions or personal interest;
- Information manipulation and false conclusions;
- Errors in strategic planning;
- Populist and short-term approaches in public policy.

Therefore, critical thinking should be an integral part of professional competence for a political leader, deputy, diplomat, or analyst.

To improve the quality of political decisions, it is necessary to systematically develop critical thinking. There are several ways to do this:

1. Analytical trainings and courses of logical analysis - form a culture of argumentative thinking in politicians and civil servants.
2. Scenario analysis - allows for the preliminary modeling of the consequences of alternative decisions.
3. The Delphi method is a method of collecting expert opinions anonymously and drawing general logical conclusions.
4. Information Critical Filters - a system for assessing the reliability of sources used for political decisions.
5. Culture of political debate - reaching new solutions by analyzing different points of view on a logical basis.

American psychologist D. Kahneman writes in his work “Thinking, Fast and Slow”: “In the human mind, systems of rapid (emotional) and slow (analytical)

thinking compete; for politics, the latter - slow but thorough thinking - is more important" [5]. Therefore, political decisions should be formed not as "quick intuitive" decisions, but as "analytically justified" decisions.

In recent years, in the process of modernizing public administration in Uzbekistan, special attention has been paid to the principles of analytical thinking and logical analysis. Presidential decrees emphasize the need for a "scientifically based, factual, and rational approach" [6]. This is an important step towards the integration of a culture of critical thinking into the political system.

Critical thinking is the intellectual foundation of the political decision-making process. It ensures that decisions are well-founded, logically consistent, and morally responsible. Therefore:

Every political decision should be based on analysis and evidence;

Any political institution must be able to accept criticism;

The development of a culture of critical thinking is the most important condition of democratic policy.

As Aristotle said, "A person who has not tested his thought should not be in politics" [1]. In this sense, critical thinking is not only a way of thinking, but also a criterion of political responsibility.

References:

1. Aristotle. Politics. Oxford University Press, 1995.
2. Dewey, J. How We Think. D.C. Heath & Co., 1910.
3. Weber, M. Politics as a Vocation. 1919.
4. Popper, K. The Open Society and Its Enemies. Routledge, 1945.
5. Kahneman, D. Thinking, Fast and Slow. Farrar, Straus and Giroux, 2011.
6. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining "Davlat boshqaruvida analitik yondashuvni kuchaytirish to'g'risida"gi qarori, 2023-yil.